

THOMSON – HASKELL TRANSFORM FUNCTION MATLAB SCRIPT

```
function [freq, amp] = resp1d_haskell(rho, cs, eta, t, nfreq, df)
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%   Linear elastic Analysis of multiple soil layer
%   Written by Seokho Jeong
%   7 May 2007
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%% define input variables %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%   rho(density), cs(shear wave velocity), eta(damping ratio),
%   and t(thickness for each layer), n(number of frequency steps)
%   , df(frequency step)
%   last value of t (for bedrock) is ignored.
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

%clear all;close all
%rho=[1.8 1.8 1.8 1.8 1.8];
%cs_profile=[400 400 400 400 400];
%t=[3.4 3.4 3.4 3.4 3.4];
%eta=0.025*ones(1,length(t));
%eta=zeros(1,length(t));
n_layer=length(t)-1;

rho_b=rho(end);           %define density at the base
eta_b=eta(end);          %define damping ratio at the base
cs_b=cs(end);            %define shear wave velocity at the base
rho(end)=[];
eta(end)=[];
cs(end)=[];
t(end)=[];

d_omega=2*pi*df;         %define frequency-step
omega=0:d_omega:d_omega*(nfreq-1); %define omega vector (frequency range)
freq=omega./(2*pi);
freq=freq';
% s_base=fft(a_input, nfreq);
%out_in=2;                %define whether or not, the input motion is rock
outcropping motion
                        %'1' for an outcropping rock motion
                        %and '2' for Inside non-outcropping motion
%pga_b=max(abs(a_input)); % 3.3354;           %define peak acceleration
at the base rock
%h_wt=200;                %define the depth of water table
kg_b=rho_b*cs_b.*omega.*sqrt(1+2i*eta_b); %% Calculation of k_b*g_b
%mod_s_max=rho.*cs_profile.^2; %calculation of maximum shear modulus vector
%mod_s=mod_s_max;
%cs_0=cs_profile;
%cs=cs_profile;

%% Calculation of Haskell-Thompson matrices
for n_l=1:n_layer
    for n_w=1:nfreq/2+1
        n_ome=n_w*d_omega;
        %% m_ht is haskell thompson matrices for each layer
        %% at each frequency step
    end
end
```

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m_ht(:,:,n_l,n_w)=[cos(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*t(n_l))...

1./(rho(n_l)*cs(n_l)*n_ome*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*sin(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i
*eta(n_l))).*t(n_l));...

-
(rho(n_l)*cs(n_l)*n_ome*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*sin(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i*et
a(n_l))).*t(n_l))...
    cos(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*t(n_l));
    %% m_ht is haskell thompson matrices for each layer,
    %% but with 1/2 height of each layer

m_ht2(:,:,n_l,n_w)=[cos(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*t(n_l)./2)...

1./(rho(n_l)*cs(n_l)*n_ome*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*sin(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i
*eta(n_l))).*t(n_l)./2);...

-
(rho(n_l)*cs(n_l)*n_ome*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*sin(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i*et
a(n_l))).*t(n_l)./2)...
    cos(n_ome/(cs(n_l)*sqrt(1+2i*eta(n_l))).*t(n_l)./2)];
    end
end

%% multiple of each H-T matrix
mm_ht=m_ht(:,:,n_layer,:);
for n_ome=1:nfreq/2+1
    for n=n_layer-1:-1:1
        mm_ht(:,:,1,n_ome)=mm_ht(:,:,1,n_ome)*m_ht(:,:,n,n_ome);
    end
end

%% Extraction of B_11 B_21 from 4-d Haskell-Thomson matrix
for iter=1:nfreq/2+1
    v_1(iter)=mm_ht(1,1,1,iter);
    v_2(iter)=mm_ht(2,1,1,iter);
end

%% Calculation of amplification function

amp(1:floor(nfreq/2)+1)=i.*kg_b(1:floor(nfreq/2)+1)./(i.*kg_b(1:floor(nfreq/2
)+1).*v_1(1:floor(nfreq/2)+1)+v_2(1:floor(nfreq/2)+1));
amp(floor(nfreq/2)+2:nfreq)=conj(amp(ceil(nfreq/2):-1:2));
amp(1)=1;
amp=amp';

%a_out=ifft(sa_fs, 'symmetric');

%dlmwrite('transfer.dat', [omega'/(2*pi) amp'], 'delimiter', '\t',
'precision', 16);
%dlmwrite('out_a.dat', [t_out' a_out'], 'delimiter', '\t', 'precision', 16);

%a0=(omega/(2*pi)*600/2286);

```

DECONVOLUTION MATLAB SCRIPT

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%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%   Linear elastic Analysis of multiple soil layer
%   Written by Seokho Jeong
%   7 May 2007
%   edited by Anna Kowal latest 10 Feb 2020 to reflect deconvolution fot
%   ground motion simulation run using SCEC BBP - Mojave veolocity profile
%   down to 200 m
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%% define input variables %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%   rho(density), cs_0(shear wave velocity), eta(damping ratio),
%   and h_l(height for each layer) are vectors where each element
%   is corresponing to each layer.
%   For example, if densities are 1.9, 2 and 2.3 for the first,
%   second and third layer, respectively, just put'rho=[1.9 2 2.3]'
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

% mass density, thicknesses, Vp, Vs, updated for Mojave velocity profile
% as defined in SCEC BBP file descripton

clear all;close all
% Mass density [Mg/m3] (or [cm/g3])
rho=[2.0 2.1 2.1 2.1 2.2 2.3 2.4];

% Cs = shear wave velocity [m/s]
cs_1=[450 650 850 950 1150 1400 1700];

% Cp = P wave velocity [m/s]
cp_1=[1700 1800 1800 1900 2000 2800 3400];

system('mkdir out_vel')

% t=thickness [m]
t=[2.0 4.0 6.0 8.0 10.0 70.0 100.0];

% eta = critical damping ratio
% 0.025 = 25% critical damping ratio
% critical damping ratio = 1/2Q so Q for this example is 20
eta=[0.025*ones(1,length(t)), 0.025];

% specify the number of points
n_old=20480;
n_input=2*n_old;
%dt=inputmotion(2,1)-inputmotion(1,1);
%dt=0.005;
%dt to be used for Taieri Site, Hyde Fault
dt=0.01
%time = 0:dt:dt*(n_old-1);
time_out = 0:dt:dt*(n_input-1);
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% frequency step
df=1/(n_input*dt)

% Calculate the 1D transfer function
[freq, amp_1] = resp1d_haskell(rho, cs_1, eta, t, n_input, df);
[freq, amp_3] = resp1d_haskell(rho, cp_1, eta, t, n_input, df);

% Plot the transfer function
figure
plot(freq, abs(amp_1), 'k', 'linewidth', 2); hold on
title('Transfer Function');
%ylabel('Frequency [Hz]');
xlabel('Frequency [Hz]');
print -depsc -tiff -r300 1dtransfer
print -dpng -r600 1dtransfer

%list_x1 = dir('02_a-Taieri-Akatore-NS.out');
%list_x2 = dir('02_b-Taieri-Akatore-EW.out');
%list_x3 = dir('02_c-Taieri-Akatore-UD.out');

list_x1 = dir('05_a-Taieri-Hyde-NS.out');
list_x2 = dir('05_b-Taieri-Hyde-EW.out');
list_x3 = dir('05_c-Taieri-Hyde-UD.out');

for ii=1:length(list_x1)
    vel_x1 = dlmread(list_x1(ii).name);
    vel_x2 = dlmread(list_x2(ii).name);
    vel_x3 = dlmread(list_x3(ii).name);
    n_old = length(vel_x1);
    % Apply tuckey window (tapered cosine function) to taper the time series
    vel_x1 = tukeywin(n_old, 0.2).*vel_x1;
    vel_x2 = tukeywin(n_old, 0.2).*vel_x2;
    vel_x3 = tukeywin(n_old, 0.2).*vel_x3;
    time = 0:dt:dt*(n_old-1);
    % Calculate the Fourier transform of the motions
    Svel_x1 = fft(vel_x1, n_input);
    Svel_x2 = fft(vel_x2, n_input);
    Svel_x3 = fft(vel_x3, n_input);
    % Calculate the Fourier transform of incident waves
    Svel_x1_out = Svel_x1./amp_1;
    Svel_x2_out = Svel_x2./amp_1;
    Svel_x3_out = Svel_x3./amp_3;
    % Inverse Fourier transform to obtain the time domain incident wave
    % time series
    vel_x1_out = ifft(Svel_x1_out, 'symmetric');
    vel_x2_out = ifft(Svel_x2_out, 'symmetric');
    vel_x3_out = ifft(Svel_x3_out, 'symmetric');

    % Store all the deconvolved incident wave time series in the output
    folder
    dlmwrite(['out_vel/', list_x1(ii).name], vel_x1_out);
    dlmwrite(['out_vel/', list_x2(ii).name], vel_x2_out);
    dlmwrite(['out_vel/', list_x3(ii).name], vel_x3_out);

    figure
    subplot(3,1,1)
```

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```
plot(time, vel_x1, 'k', 'linewidth', 1); hold on;
plot(time_out, vel_x1_out, 'r', 'linewidth', 1);
axis([-inf 70 -.25 .21])
grid on
set(gca, 'xminorgrid', 'on')
set(gca, 'MinorGridLineStyle', '--')
ylabel('Vs (sec/m2)', 'fontsize', 16)
subplot(3,1,2)
plot(time, vel_x2, 'k', 'linewidth', 1); hold on;
plot(time_out, vel_x2_out, 'r', 'linewidth', 1);
axis([-inf 70 -.2 .12])
grid on
set(gca, 'xminorgrid', 'on')
set(gca, 'MinorGridLineStyle', '--')
ylabel('Vs (sec/m2)', 'fontsize', 16)
subplot(3,1,3)
plot(time, vel_x3, 'k', 'linewidth', 1); hold on;
plot(time_out, vel_x3_out, 'r', 'linewidth', 1);
axis([-inf 70 -.17 .25])
grid on
set(gca, 'xminorgrid', 'on')
set(gca, 'MinorGridLineStyle', '--')
lgd = legend ('before deconvolution', 'after deconvolution');
lgd.FontSize = 20;
xlabel('time (sec)', 'fontsize', 16)
ylabel('Vs (sec/m2)', 'fontsize', 16)
```

end